

Temporal features estimated from electromyographic and inertial signals for the assessment of bradykinesia in people with Parkinson's disease

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Abstract— Several motor disorders can cause the slowness of voluntary movements, known as bradykinesia. For instance, in people with Parkinson's disease (PD) the evaluation of bradykinesia together with other cardinal signs are of great relevance for the diagnosis and follow-up of the disorder. In this context, the development of methods for the objective assessment of bradykinesia is relevant. This research proposes the use of temporal features extracted from electromyographic and inertial signals for the evaluation of bradykinesia. Data were collected from six people with Parkinson's disease who executed pronation/supination and flexion/extension of the hand, and pinch movement. The overall mean time of distinct features were estimated for each participant, characterizing, thus, typical values of the features for the studied sample. The participants were ranked according to their mean temporal features, illustrating that this parameter can be used as an objective measure for the evaluation of bradykinesia. In the future, the proposed method should be applied to a larger group of people with Parkinson's disease and a healthy control group so that it is possible to characterize the temporal features adequately.

Keywords— Parkinson's disease, bradykinesia, electromyography, inertial signals.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinsonism encompasses a wide range of diseases with reduced multiple monoaminergic systems, including dopaminergic, cholinergic, serotonergic, and noradrenergic system deficits [1]. PD is subdivided into: primary, secondary, plus and heredodegenerative parkinsonism. This paper will address primary Parkinsonism which is also known as (idiopathic) Parkinson's disease.

Parkinson's disease is a progressive and degenerative Central Nervous System (CNS) dysfunction characterized by cardinal signs, i.e., bradykinesia, tremor at rest, muscular rigidity and postural instability. In addition, patients often suffer from problems such as flexed posture, freezing, depression, cognitive dysfunction and sleep disorders. PD is

the result of the SNpC not able to generate dopamine or the striatum no able to receive dopamine [1].

Although the cause of PD is unknown, it is believed that a combination of environmental and genetic factors plays a role in the development of the disease. The ageing process of the human body predisposes to a reduction of dopamine in the CNS [2], this deficiency causes changes in body movements, making them slower and unbalanced, reduced control, and with reduced muscular strength.

There are several types of scales to determine the severity of disease progression in patients. The Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS) is the most widely used in clinical and scientific communities for assessing motor impairment and disability. The UPDRS has several assessment questions that receive a response ranging from 0 to 4, where: (0) normal, (1) mild, (2) moderate, (3) severe, and (4) rigorous. With these answers, through a questionnaire applied to the patient or guardian, the general state of the disease is defined and enables comparison between groups of individuals [3].

Bradykinesia is a hallmark of disturbances in the basal ganglia and is characterized by difficulties in the planning, initiation and execution of movement, and also in performing sequential, repetitive and simultaneous activities [4]. The first sign is usually slowness while performing daily activities, consequently increasing the reaction times of individuals. This slowness also affects fine movements such as using a remote control and buttoning a shirt. Other manifestations resulting from bradykinesia are: loss of facial expressions, reduction of spontaneous movements and arm swing during gait, and monotonic and hypophonic dysarthria [1, 5, 6]. As these symptoms are easier for the patient to identify, bradykinesia becomes one of the ways to recognize the disease before neurological diagnosis.

In this study, a toolbox so-called PDPack (<https://github.com/aoandrade/PDPack.git>) is employed for the estimate of temporal features extracted from electromyographic (EMG) and inertial signals collected from people with PD. A major feature of the toolbox is that it

employs a unique signal processing strategy for the analysis of both EMG and inertial signals.

The intention of this pilot research is to determine basic descriptive statistics of the feature values so that in the future the sample size can be increased, allowing thus a comparison between healthy and unhealthy groups.

II. METHODOLOGY

This is an experimental clinical study conducted at the Center for Innovation and Technological Assessment in Health (NIATS) of the Federal University of Uberlândia (UFU), Uberlândia, MG, Brazil. The study was approved by the local Human Research Ethics Committee (CAAE: 65165416.4.0000.5152)

Electromyographic and inertial signals were collected from six people with PD at the Parkinson's Triangle Association (Uberlândia, Brazil), five male and one female, by performing three consecutive trials of data collection for each individual. For this study, UPDRS scores were not available, hence, although the individuals have PD it was not possible to guarantee the presence of bradykinesia.

The sensors were positioned on the region of the *First Dorsal Interosseous*. Data collections consisted of each individual performing the following tasks: pinch, hand opening and closing, pronation and supination, and flexion and extension of the wrist. Fig. 1 illustrates the sequence of tasks.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the sequence of tasks for each type of movement. EXT is a hardware-based annotation which defined the beginning and end of each task.

For EMG signal acquisition, the 16-bit Intan RHD2216 (Intan Technologies, LLC) system with a 5,000 Hz sampling rate with differential amplification was used.

In this study, the TREMSEN (Precise Tremor Sensing Technology) system (National Institute of Intellectual Property - Brazil - BR 10 2014 023282 6) was used for data acquisition and real-time visualization of the inertial signals. The system has inertial measurement units (IMUs) composed of a gyroscope (L3G4200D, STMicroelectronics, Switzerland) and an accelerometer-magnetometer combined unit (LSM303DLM, STMicroelectronics, Switzerland). These are compact, low power consumption sensors mounted on a 20 mm × 13 mm × 3 mm board, making them suitable for integration in wearable devices. The mass of the sensor board is only 0.9 grams. The IMUs are connected to a microcontroller by wires.

Signal processing was executed offline by using the PD-Pack toolbox for R. The sequence of steps employed to process these signals were: data visualization, signal processing, event detection and feature extraction. The PD-Pack toolbox was used for the automatic estimate of the following temporal parameters from EMG and inertial

signals: Time Interval Between Peaks (PPI), Time Interval Between Valleys (VVI) and Time Interval Between Peaks and Valleys (PVI).

The mean and standard deviation of each feature were estimated for each subject and sensor. The overall mean was estimated for each subject. The results consider the joint analysis of all executed tasks.

III. RESULTS

Fig. 2 shows a typical signal detected from the X axis of the gyroscope during the execution the experimental tasks. As expected, for this sensor and axis, the angular velocity is larger for the pronation/supination and flexion/extension tasks.

Fig. 2. X axis of signals obtained from the gyroscope. The regions of signal activity correspond to the execution of movements shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3 shows typical results of a filtered signal estimated by the PD-Pack toolbox. Similar results are found even for EMG signals, making the process of identification of peaks and valleys easier.

Fig. 3. Typical results obtained from the PD-Pack. For clarity the interval between 0 and 9.5 s is presented. The oscillatory signal corresponds to the filtered signal. The upper and lower vertical bars are the peak and valleys detected.

TABLE I. TABLE WITH TIME INTERVALS BETWEEN PEAKS

Sensor/Subject	Time Interval Between Peaks (PPI) – Mean (s) ± Standard Deviation (s)					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
ACC1.X	0.665 ± 0.324	0.644 ± 0.265	0.644 ± 0.259	0.567 ± 0.329	0.744 ± 0.377	0.654 ± 0.322
ACC1.Y	0.752 ± 0.372	0.758 ± 0.376	0.724 ± 0.311	0.717 ± 0.320	0.766 ± 0.359	0.744 ± 0.345
ACC1.Z	0.745 ± 0.337	0.655 ± 0.244	0.696 ± 0.25	0.681 ± 0.287	0.750 ± 0.352	0.722 ± 0.281
EMG1	0.692 ± 0.324	0.631 ± 0.237	0.673 ± 0.285	0.661 ± 0.236	0.629 ± 0.213	0.660 ± 0.247
GYR1.X	0.689 ± 0.275	0.676 ± 0.268	0.695 ± 0.242	0.603 ± 0.204	0.717 ± 0.323	0.683 ± 0.245
GYR1.Y	0.633 ± 0.212	0.660 ± 0.247	0.678 ± 0.249	0.588 ± 0.227	0.762 ± 0.332	0.744 ± 0.311
GYR1.Z	0.673 ± 0.170	0.701 ± 0.302	0.635 ± 0.233	0.486 ± 0.228	0.689 ± 0.237	0.747 ± 0.326
MAG1.X	0.699 ± 0.291	0.795 ± 0.318	0.709 ± 0.267	0.688 ± 0.391	0.701 ± 0.330	0.821 ± 0.372
MAG1.Y	0.729 ± 0.382	0.737 ± 0.304	0.778 ± 0.381	0.766 ± 0.456	0.768 ± 0.289	0.823 ± 0.351
MAG1.Z	0.679 ± 0.280	0.805 ± 0.352	0.717 ± 0.249	0.756 ± 0.422	0.778 ± 0.291	0.765 ± 0.326
Total Mean	0.696	0.706	0.695	0.651	0.730	0.736

TABLE II. TABLE WITH TIME INTERVALS BETWEEN VALLEYS

Sensor/Subject	Time Interval Between Valleys (VVI) – Mean (s) ± Standard Deviation (s)					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
ACC1.X	0.671 ± 0.316	0.652 ± 0.254	0.642 ± 0.251	0.572 ± 0.341	0.704 ± 0.286	0.650 ± 0.330
ACC1.Y	0.755 ± 0.363	0.792 ± 0.374	0.741 ± 0.339	0.736 ± 0.346	0.784 ± 0.470	0.739 ± 0.352
ACC1.Z	0.739 ± 0.346	0.668 ± 0.263	0.689 ± 0.240	0.699 ± 0.312	0.734 ± 0.444	0.713 ± 0.262
EMG1	0.690 ± 0.301	0.628 ± 0.232	0.676 ± 0.300	0.651 ± 0.236	0.624 ± 0.231	0.658 ± 0.253
GYR1.X	0.699 ± 0.266	0.684 ± 0.279	0.716 ± 0.233	0.604 ± 0.235	0.702 ± 0.357	0.684 ± 0.241
GYR1.Y	0.635 ± 0.215	0.659 ± 0.250	0.669 ± 0.246	0.588 ± 0.201	0.739 ± 0.285	0.745 ± 0.318
GYR1.Z	0.674 ± 0.180	0.711 ± 0.315	0.636 ± 0.231	0.487 ± 0.230	0.703 ± 0.250	0.752 ± 0.293
MAG1.X	0.698 ± 0.279	0.792 ± 0.320	0.711 ± 0.266	0.689 ± 0.410	0.688 ± 0.284	0.809 ± 0.364
MAG1.Y	0.715 ± 0.318	0.759 ± 0.286	0.792 ± 0.375	0.750 ± 0.454	0.749 ± 0.270	0.810 ± 0.360
MAG1.Z	0.679 ± 0.269	0.827 ± 0.388	0.733 ± 0.251	0.760 ± 0.424	0.770 ± 0.272	0.775 ± 0.313
Total Mean	0.696	0.717	0.700	0.653	0.719	0.733

TABLE III. TABLE WITH TIME INTERVALS BETWEEN PEAKS AND VALLEYS

Sensor/Subject	Time Interval Between Peaks and Valleys (PVI) – Mean (s) ± Standard Deviation (s)					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
ACC1.X	0.349 ± 0.238	0.327 ± 0.16	0.354 ± 0.217	0.298 ± 0.212	0.411 ± 0.294	0.336 ± 0.272
ACC1.Y	0.386 ± 0.247	0.357 ± 0.205	0.395 ± 0.281	0.356 ± 0.220	0.363 ± 0.252	0.391 ± 0.282
ACC1.Z	0.362 ± 0.221	0.329 ± 0.156	0.34 ± 0.156	0.344 ± 0.220	0.377 ± 0.230	0.348 ± 0.190
EMG1	0.341 ± 0.173	0.308 ± 0.150	0.334 ± 0.135	0.324 ± 0.144	0.321 ± 0.151	0.321 ± 0.140
GYR1.X	0.333 ± 0.146	0.325 ± 0.167	0.341 ± 0.17	0.300 ± 0.141	0.345 ± 0.150	0.339 ± 0.151
GYR1.Y	0.324 ± 0.139	0.322 ± 0.151	0.351 ± 0.175	0.297 ± 0.127	0.371 ± 0.158	0.363 ± 0.233
GYR1.Z	0.346 ± 0.118	0.339 ± 0.168	0.334 ± 0.162	0.234 ± 0.134	0.335 ± 0.173	0.382 ± 0.196
MAG1.X	0.363 ± 0.188	0.390 ± 0.177	0.369 ± 0.203	0.356 ± 0.282	0.386 ± 0.272	0.416 ± 0.240
MAG1.Y	0.363 ± 0.218	0.363 ± 0.180	0.411 ± 0.268	0.394 ± 0.280	0.421 ± 0.246	0.427 ± 0.295
MAG1.Z	0.348 ± 0.181	0.395 ± 0.196	0.334 ± 0.168	0.359 ± 0.185	0.369 ± 0.184	0.391 ± 0.204
Total Mean	0.352	0.346	0.356	0.326	0.370	0.371

Based on the detected peaks and valleys it is possible to estimate the features PPI, VVI and PVI, which can be used as an objective measurement of bradykinesia. Tables I, II and III show the estimated mean and standard deviation of these features for each subject, sensor and axis (for the case of the inertial sensor).

According to Tables I and II, it can be observed that the time intervals for the occurrence of peaks and valleys for the same individual have similar values. In Table III, the intervals presented lower values indicating shorter distance between a peak and valley of an event.

Through the overall average it is possible to determine which individual has a longer time interval and, therefore, a slower movement.

Thus, sorting in descending order the mean values of PPI, VVI and PVI, the individuals are ranked as: 6, 5, 2, 3, 1 and 4. This indicates that individual 6 has the highest slowness of movement whereas subject 4 has the lowest one.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Bradykinesia is a condition present in several motor disorders. In the context of PD its detection and follow-up are relevant for the appropriate treatment of the disorder. EMG and inertial signals are methods used for clinical analysis of movements, especially in understanding the mechanisms that the CNS uses to perform motor tasks.

This preliminary study employed the PD-Pack toolbox for the estimate of temporal features from people with PD. The relatively high standard deviations indicate a high variability during the execution of the motor tasks. This variability can be related to the fact that the results were not given by tasks separately, however further studies are necessary, as high variability can be an indicative of low motor performance [7]. Further studies should also include results per tasks.

For its complete validation, it is necessary to increase the number of subjects of the study, and to include data from healthy individuals for comparison. Future experiments should also include a correlation analysis between UPDRS scores with the temporal features (PPI, VVI and PVI). As there is no reported study in the literature showing typical values of those temporal features, the results presented in Tables I to III can be useful for guiding new studies and experimental protocols.

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